

SPACE MANAGEMENT IN DEVELOPING DENTITION USING SPACE MAINTAINER- TWO CASE REPORTS

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ABSTRACT

Premature loss of Primary Molars may result in undesirable movements of primary and permanent teeth, leading to space loss and arch length insufficiency. Premature loss of Primary Molars often leads to disturbances of the developing dentition. The space loss which has occur subsequently, can produce or increase the severity of malocclusions, such as crowding and unfavourable molar relationships. In cases of bilateral premature loss of multiple primary molars, there will be difficulty in chewing food which will affect the normal growth and development of the child. The purpose of this case reports is to describe conventional space maintainers used to maintain the space after premature loss of primary teeth in maxillary and mandibular arch.

KEYWORDS

Space Maintainer, Primary Teeth, Pediatric Dentistry

INTRODUCTION

Premature loss of Primary Molars may result in undesirable movements of primary and permanent teeth, leading to space loss and arch length insufficiency¹. Premature loss of Primary Molars often leads to disturbances of the developing dentition. The space loss which has occur subsequently, can produce or increase the severity of malocclusions, such as crowding and unfavourable molar relationships.² In cases of bilateral premature loss of multiple primary molars, there will be difficulty in chewing food which will affect the normal growth and development of the child.³ This space loss also cause the unerupted permanent tooth to erupt buccally or lingually or may remain impacted.⁴ The amount of space loss in the mandible is more considerable than in the amount of space lost in the maxilla after premature loss of the primary tooth⁵⁻⁷ Moreover, the space loss could be higher if a primary second rather than primary first molar was lost⁸

In order to prevent wastage of arch length, an appliance is given know as space maintainer. It is employed after a premature loss of the primary tooth.⁹ Space maintainers presently in use include either fixed space maintainers or removable space maintainers. Although removable space maintainer is easy to fabricate and restore various functions such as aesthetic and mastication, but removable space maintainers are lost more frequently than fixed space maintainers.^{10,11} Fixed space maintainers have a suitable success rate. Fixed space maintainers have various disadvantages such as cement dissolution; solder failure, caries formation along the margins of the band, and long construction time.¹²

Space maintainers regardless of the design chosen, should fulfil number of necessary requirements, such as maintaining the desired interproximal space, not interference with occlusion of opponent teeth or with the eruption of the permanent tooth, it should allow sufficient mesiodistal space for the alignment of the permanent tooth eruption, not inferring

in phonetics as well as mastication and should be easy to clean.¹²Traditionally, the treatment of choice for bilateral space loss in mandibular arch is the placement of a Lingual arch space maintainer and the treatment of choice for bilateral space loss in the maxillary arch is the placement of a Nance Palatal arch space maintainer. The purpose of this case reports is to describe conventional space maintainers used to maintain the space after premature loss of primary teeth in maxillary and mandibular arch.

CASE REPORT- 1

A 9 years old male patient visited to the Department with chief complaint of pain in lower right and left back region of jaw since 2 months. Pain was dull aching and intermittent in nature. Pain aggravated on mastication and relieved on rest. There was no relevant history of any form of major illness, allergies or any hospitalization reported by parents. On examination. Deep proximal caries with 74 and 84 were present. Tenderness on percussion and mobility was present with 74 and 84. Deep occlusal and proximal caries was present with 75. Patient gave a history of visit to private clinic where temporary ZOE dressing was given with 85. Pit and fissure caries was present with 36 and 46 (Figure 1 and Figure 2). Radiograph showed root resorption with 74 and 84 and deep occlusal caries with 75 and 85. (Figure 3 and Figure 4). Treatment plan was Oral Prophylaxis and GIC restoration with 75 and 85, Pit and fissure sealants with 36 and 46 and Extraction was planned with 74 and 84 under local anaesthesia. Band adaptation with 75 and 85 followed by Lingual arch space maintainer with 75 and 85. (Figure 5).

Figure-1 - Maxillary occlusal view

Figure-2 - Mandibular occlusal view showing deep proximal caries with 74 and 84, occlusal caries with 75 and temporary ZOE dressing with 85

Figure-3 - IOPA showing deep proximal caries with 74 and deep occlusal caries with 75

Figure 4 - IOPA showing deep proximal caries with 74 and deep occlusal caries with 85

Figure-5- Lingual arch space maintainer with 75 and 85.

CASE REPORT- 2

An 8 years old female patient visited to the department with chief complaint of pain in upper right and left back region of jaw since 1 month. Pain was dull aching and intermittent in nature. Pain aggravated on mastication and relieved on rest. There was no relevant history of any form of major illness, allergies or any hospitalization reported by parents. On examination grossly decayed 54 and 64 were present. Tenderness on percussion and mobility was present with 54 and 64. Physiologic mobility was present with 61. GIC restoration was done with 85. (Figure 6 and Figure 7). Radiograph showed root resorption with 54 and 64. (Figure 8 and Figure 9). Treatment plan was Oral Prophylaxis and GIC restoration with 75. Extraction with 54 and 64 under local anaesthesia and Band adaptation with 55 and 65 followed by Nance palatal arch space maintainer was planned. (Figure 10).

Figure-6 -Maxillary occlusal view showing proximal caries with 54, 64

Figure-7 -Mandibular occlusal view

Figure-8-IOPA with 54 showing deep proximal caries

Figure-9- IOPA with 64 showing deep proximal caries

Figure-10-Cementation of Nance Palatal Arch
Space Maintainer with 55 and 65.

DISCUSSION

The approach for management of space in the both primary dentition and mixed dentition is to first understand the problem to plan treatment for the child. The subsequent treatment differs from whether maxillary region is involved or mandibular region. Loss in the anterior region is usually due to trauma, which is common when the child is learning to walk. Nursing bottle caries or rampant caries would be the reason for loss of anterior and posterior teeth.¹⁴ Other cause of space loss within an arch is primary teeth with interproximal caries followed by loss of primary molars when there is no proper space management.¹⁵ The degree of space loss varies according to the arch, site in the arch, and time elapsed since tooth loss.¹⁶ Therefore, loss of space in the dental arch that interferes with the desired eruption of the permanent teeth may require evaluation and early intervention. For the maintenance of tooth loss spaces indicated is the use of various space maintainers used in maxillary or mandibular arch.¹⁷

The Nance palatal button is a fixed orthodontic appliance supported dental-mucus, which is suitable for multiple and bilateral loss of molars in maxillary arch. It also serves as intraoral anchoring mechanism. It helps in anchoring the upper arch during the alignment phase and also anchorage for retraction of the premolars and canines. It also allows various modifications to the original device. Various rakes can be incorporated in nance palatal button which serves as a habit breaking appliance.¹⁸

Exfoliation of the mandibular primary molars is usually expected during late mixed dentition period, so space preservation becomes more crucial if leeway space utilization is planned to resolve expected crowding as well as to preserve space for the future succedaneous teeth.¹⁹ A lower lingual arch is usually recommended as a holding device which will help to maintain mandibular arch length and also to prevent mesial migration of the mandibular first molars.²⁰ **Brennan and Gianelly** studied the efficiency of a lower lingual arch in the mixed dentition stage to preserve arch length and they concluded that the preservation of arch length using lingual arch has resolved crowding in 68 per cent of subjects.¹⁹ **Rebellato** have also investigated the efficiency of a lingual arch space maintainer in preventing mesial migration of the first permanent molars. They reported that the lingual arch reduced arch perimeter loss but at the expense of mandibular incisor proclination.²¹ **Villalobos** treated 32 patients with a lower lingual arch to control arch perimeter and concluded that the lingual arch is an effective appliance for preserving arch length.²²

The present case reports explains about management of bilateral space loss in developing dentition in maxillary or mandibular arch using Nance palatal arch space maintainer and Lingual arch space maintainer.

CONCLUSION

Dental space maintenance is essential in cases of premature loss of primary dentition to prevent any form of malposition or crowding of the developing permanent teeth. There are various types of space maintainers available and each type is particularly designated for particular indications. Space maintainers are fixed, semi-fixed, or removable, with or without loops, wires, and/or bands, unilateral or bilateral, and are placed on mandibular or maxillary arches. Space maintainer used for bilateral space loss in mandible includes fixed Lingual arches and for maxillary arch includes Nance palatal Space maintainers. This case series explained both of them.

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